

PERFORMATIVE ARCHITECTURES FOR OFF-GRID COMMUNITIES

Design Methodologies for Self-Sufficient
Housing Solutions

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ABSTRACT

Climate change and rising energy poverty reclaim the urgency for a new connection between design and energy. As a matter of fact, energy justice for vulnerable communities highlights the structural inequalities in the capitalist energy provision worldwide, also considering that 9.3% of EU citizens were not able to heat their homes properly in the last two years. Beyond the political debate on energy price cap and provision, a new approach is needed to generate new performative building typologies towards off-grid communities. Therefore, the article will focus on an interdisciplinary design methodology to shape a new architectural approach based on self-sufficiency criteria. The paper shows the design methodology applied in research, teaching and practice over the years in different contexts.

1. INTRODUCTION

As recently reported in the European Green Deal project, sustainable buildings in European countries will drive to achieve decarbonisation and define a clean energy system. Considering the building stock in Europe scenario, buildings are responsible for about 40% of total energy consumption in the EU and 36% of greenhouse gas emissions from energy. As a matter of fact, 85% of EU buildings were built before 2000, and amongst those, 75% have a poor energy performance. Therefore, it has been highlighted in the EU Green Deal as an essential point to drive energy efficiency in the sector and obtain demanded results. (European Commission, 2020).

10,6% of Europeans were unable to keep their homes adequately warm in 2024, and the last Conference on Energy Poverty confirmed the trend of increasing energy poverty. In the last years, energy poverty was introduced in the literature to outline the indication of domestic energy deprivation or vulnerability (Castaño-Rosa et al., 2019). In 2016, the Commission launched the Energy Poverty Observatory (EPOV) to monitor it and also to spearhead the academic community and start a poverty diagnosis. Energy poverty is a complex and multidimensional issue that lies at the intersection between household income, energy costs and the energy efficiency of household appliances (Faiella et al., 2019). The term “reflects a long history of “on the ground”, grassroots practice and policy proposals that centre on energy and the environment in a changing climate marked by growing social inequalities.” (Jenkins et al. 2016) and “introduce energy justice as a framework that evaluates (a) where injustices emerge, (b) which affected sections of society are ignored, and (c) which processes exist for their remediation in order to (i) reveal and (ii) reduce such injustices.”

With the complex scenario of issues related to climate change and energy crises, in research, as well as in education and practice, the energy topic is crucial if associated with design buildings, starting from the large residential building sector.

A radical approach is needed from the design process to the construction phase, considering the householders not as a single user but as a part of a community to create a shorter energy cycle that includes a process of saving and production. This also develops alternative economic models where communities could become more accountable for saving, producing, and sharing. With an approach to share resources, and self-produce their energy, shifting their role from consumers to producers with the possibility of being off the grid, so with an autonomous system outside the urban water and energy

supply. The paper collects different projects and explains the approach to this topic through practice, research and teaching.

2. TOWARDS OFF-GRID COMMUNITIES

2.1. PRACTICE

The paper is a critical compendium of applied research and projects realized during the years through our practice CODESIGNLAB; such work deals with diverse programmatic agendas from temporary dwellings to affordable housing, cultural centres, etc.

The filrouge of these experimentations is addressing the question of self-sufficiency as a design driver for performative architectures. Therefore, if some of the projects mainly deal with a strategy based on reducing energy consumption, the most challenging ones are integrating an energy production approach.

2.2. OFF-GRID ARCHITECTURES

The topic of self-sufficiency was experimented within an inter-scalar approach responding to different climatic and social contexts.

The smart shell project is one of the first investigation on temporary housing for emergency scenarios. Therefore, we have developed a design-to-build protocol for a “smart shell”, a fast-deployment housing solution conceived as a transportable and energetically self-sufficient device. The design process investigated the relation between high-tech design and low-tech construction; the kinetic systems offer a large catalogue of different prototypical shapes and dimensions that could adapt to different needs and contexts. The project is a foldable modular structural system made of timber and covered by tailor made strips of photovoltaic Teflon membrane made out of an amorphous siliceous system. The kinetic movements of the structure are functional to keep the performance of the PV system high, according to different climatic conditions and orientations, to respond to the energy users’ needs. The membrane PV membrane is waterproof and provides some interesting overshadowing performances, filtrating the solar radiation inside the dwelling.

With a similar off-grid logic but more related to a specific context and permanent use we have designed and built the African Fabbers House in Douala (Cameroon). The project was realised in the framework of the Camon project (2019) as part of an applied research agenda developed in collaboration with our African Fabbers School students. The housing prototype is the result of a research on the Logbaba slum housing conditions in relation to energy and water accessibility. Therefore, the prototype was inspired by the local informal dwellings with the aim to upgrade such spontaneous system in relation to their environmental performances for a more healthy and sustainable living based on the self-production of energy, water and food.

Figure 1: Smart shell World Urban Forum (UN-Habitat) / CODESIGNALB

The construction system is conceived to develop a circular economy approach and to be entirely realised with local material systems, easy to assemble, customise and replicate. Therefore, the design and fabrication processes were developed in Cameroon through a number of training programmes with local students, craftsmen and partners to evolve indigenous technologies. The project follows some local vernacular bioclimatic principles on passive ventilation to minimise the use of air-conditioned, taking advantage of the local solar radiation dynamics to produce energy out of renewable sources. The off-grid strategy is combining different strategies: the roof is conceived for both collecting rainwater and producing solar energy with affordable photovoltaics, and the façade system is designed as an ecological skin providing passive cooling ventilation for such hot and humid tropical climates. This responds to different informal spatial configurations and users' needs by processing natural material systems available on site such as wood, ceramics and bamboo.

In year 2020 we have started to develop a similar environmental design approach for another public building typology, the Cultural Hub in Douala. The project was financed by the AICS Italian Agency for International Cooperation; the building project came from a series of self-production workshops for and with the local communities. Working with an evolutionary approach to the traditional techniques and designing work tools to transform raw materials on site.

2.3. OFF-GRID ARCHITECTURAL COMPONENTS

The design and research are also applied at the scale of the architectural component, through an off-grid strategy with the idea of producing or performing for the building.

2.4. CERAMICA PERFORMATIVA

The project explores in an innovative way the relation between computational design, digital fabrication and natural semi-fluid material systems for a performative architecture. The result of such applied research on architectural fabrication and ceramic structural skins generates a porous wall that is able to modulate daylight and natural ventilation. The main goal of such experimentation is to develop a sort of water reuse system to improve the thermal building performances. Therefore, the inner cavities are designed for water circulation, creating an evaporative cooling dynamic in order to regulate thermal comfort performances and improve air quality.

Figure 4:
Ceramica performativa /
CODESIGNALB

3. TEACHING

We applied the research methodology on this topic in many experiences, here is illustrated the Paolo Cascone Masterclass at the ASA - Advanced School of Architecture (2022, Polytechnic of Milan) directed by Prof. Pierre-Alain Croset.

The Master Class at the Politecnico di Milano tested different social and climatic contexts selected by the 20 international students split into four group works. The methodology applies an integrated design approach, developed through digital environmental simulations and physical prototypes, to generate a catalogue of site-specific productive housing solutions based on the following key concepts:

1. Social scenario and housing diversified typologies:

- The housing unit typologies will have to be affordable and respond to the spatial needs of different users, including students, disadvantaged people, migrants, etc.
- The housing cluster would need to be assembled with the aim to generate mixed use programmes and shared facilities. Such social and programmatic mixity will balance the energy needs.

2. Climate and off-grid strategy:

The local climatic context informs site specific off-grid strategy according to the environmental micro-climatic analysis also in relation to local vernacular bioclimatic solutions:

- passive: thermal insulation/passive ventilation/daylight,
- active: renewable energy /water and sanitation.

3. Circularity and material systems:

- Local climate will inform the selection of main construction materials: natural and recycled. The kind of material and its physical properties will change according to what is available onsite in relation to the different climatic regions
- By selecting the different kinds of material, designers have to take into account its embodied carbon with the aim to minimise greenhouse gas emissions for the whole process.

4. Building components and ecological construction systems:

- The building components' dimensions would be related to the chosen material system; its thickness could change according to different strategies.
- The construction and assembly systems will change according to different strategies in relation to the interaction between digital manufacturing technologies and local techniques.
- The construction system could be made by a primary and secondary structure and will have to be easy to mantle and dismantle onsite.

5. Smart prefabrication and mass customisation:

- The design composition has to develop catalogues of possible variations at different scales: building component/panel variation (perforations, joints, etc.), housing units' variations, cluster variations with more units assembled horizontally and vertically,
- Each configuration has to provide an incremental strategy explaining the project's possible spatial and volumetric evolution over time.

The result of this engaging master class was shown in a final exhibition with models and drawings collected in a booklet with all the students' projects. We are developing forward this climate sensitive teaching methodology within a Prototype Fabrication and Testing approach also in the MSc and the BSc courses on Architecture and Environmental Design that we are leading at the University of Westminster.

Figure 5:
ASA-politecnico di Milano,
Masterclass P. Cascone 2022.
Temperate climate Milan –
Italy. (Students: Ara Ibrahim,
Alice Miloni, Nehir Özdemir
Selin Yavuz , Andrea Di
Tommaso, Gabriele Licciardi)

4. RESEARCH

4.1. AFRICAN OFF-GRID HOUSING

The off-grid design methodology developed in the above-mentioned case studies was evolved and integrated also thanks to the African Off-grid Housing research project (UKRI funded) in the years 2020-2021. The AOH research agenda was based on the idea of producing innovative knowledge that is able to bridge traditional and advanced design strategies as well as construction technologies in response to the need for sustainable and performative housing in Sub-Saharan Africa. The AOH research by design methodology is based on an evolutionary design approach starting from the analytical study of pre-colonial African dwellings. In particular, we have started to associate a series of vernacular examples of Cameroon vernacular architecture (geometry, material systems, etc.). Therefore, the cause-effect relationship between climate and materiality of Cameroonian vernacular architecture has been considered an architectural paradigm to be adapted and modified according to different contexts with similar climatic conditions. The relationship between the process of integration of the existing technological and material heritage with the innovative systems is based on combining a naturally ventilated system made out of natural fibres for the external skin and a thermal mass skin in terracotta for the internal skin of the core. The research has realised a catalogue of housing solutions based on the Environmental parametric design process; the information-based design methodology is developed parametrically.

Figure 6:
African Off-grid Housing
research project /AOH
research team

The result of this contextual parametric design process is a catalogue of architectural variations of the initial genotype, providing possible tailor-made solutions to be integrated into informal neighbourhoods and slums.

Furthermore, a bioclimatic strategy with a design focus is conceived as a passive way to minimize energy and water consumption.

The energy strategy is based on the idea of both minimizing the consumption of electricity (for air conditioning, etc.) and providing renewable energy according to the user's needs. With this premise, we have structured our energy parametric modelling based on the site-specific solar radiation analysis on the roof of the house prototype.

This is in order to estimate the number of PV panels and localize their best position to achieve such performances. At the same time, we have developed this tool to provide the requested energy according to different possible house orientations for the three different household sizes. Considering the statistics on the heavy precipitation in Douala and the lack of accessibility to clean water.

Therefore, we have integrated a system of rainwater collection from the roof to the tanks underneath the house to be filtered and used for water users' needs.

4.2. RENEWABLE ENERGY PRODUCTION: THE ARCHITECTURAL COMPONENT AS A DEVICE

Thanks to a grant of the QHT we have developed a more focused research project on off-grid architectural components at the University of Westminster. As part of the research-by-design methodology, two building components were developed to produce energy from renewable sources: sun and wind.

The project has involved researcher and PG students of the University of Westminster to design, prototype, test and fabricate both façade components using wasted or recycled materials to develop two productive modules at the scale of 1:1, with a dimension of 60x150 cm.

Figure 7:
The performance analysis
(Images by Anastasia
Suzdaltseva and Maddalena
Laddaga)

Figure 8:
The energy solar component
construction kit

4.3. TESTING MATERIAL AND DIFFERENT SHAPES

The design phase was associated with a material testing stage to select the right one, strong enough for outdoor use, to allocate the PV cells for the first module and for the second one to work with the wind and become a wind turbine. Many materials were tested to find the right balance between strongness and lightness, prepared to be tested outside. The component elements are assembled with joints fabricated with CNC and 3d printing.

Figure 9:
The energy wind component
construction kit

4.4. THE SUN COMPONENT

The panels are designed with six small elements as a brise soleil system. The concept is to adapt the module on a building as part of the façade or roof system, working as a brise soleil to produce energy and shadows from the sun. The components work as lighting and heating devices inside the building to improve the building's performance and the user's comfort. Every panel is connected to a circuit and a battery to collect the produced energy; the control panel and the battery are at the bottom of the frame. The system is modular and scalable.

4.5. THE WIND COMPONENT

The component is composed of 12 micro wind turbines that rotate by the wind. The turbines are built with light sheets and bars designed in two turbine columns connected with the timber frame. The two bars are connected at the bottom and with a gears' system to transform the rotation into energy.

The wind generator module was built with a double vertical axis wind turbine connected, through a gearbox, to a motor used as a generator. Regarding the turbine blades, many construction strategies have been tested; the final one is a combination of laser-cut structure and semi-rigid plastic foils.

As a work in progress, the two components are still being tested and monitored, using digital and physical tools, to improve the performance or to build new prototypes. The value of this making experience was combining both the research and educational aspects with a making session with students. The Energy generator modules have been conceptualised as architectural components to be applied to the building system as part of the community energy production system.

5. CONCLUSION

Off-grid architectural solutions offer a pathway towards a more ecological ethic in the field of architecture that prioritises a sharing economy to generate more democratic access to energy and reduce the environmental impact of centralised systems.

As a matter of fact, a new atlas of environmental tectonics is needed to respond to a new generation of householders and citizens ready to develop a shift from consumers to producers. Such an atlas would need an adequate design to build process to fabricate productive components realized by merging different technologies and assembled according to different spatial requirements into one integrated architectural device. To improve such a process, architects and stakeholders would need a more prototypical approach to fabricate and test such devices' performances and scalability. Therefore, the role of applied research will be crucial in the near future to accelerate such transition through physical experimentations in collaboration with the energy and construction industries. Such experimentation would need the creation of interdisciplinary research laboratories involving designers, environmental engineers, economists, etc. Such a change of paradigm will also make users more responsible, allowing them to optimise energy and water and to be independent and conscious about the potential of self-producing and sharing both energy and water in a communitarian system.

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